

Linear free energy relationship and conformational effects on oxidation of aromatic acetals by pyridinium fluorochromate

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Kinetics of oxidation of aromatic acetals by pyridiniumfluorochromate (PFC) in aqueous acetic acid medium reveal that the reactions are second order, first order each in [acetal] and [PFC]. The presence of electron-withdrawing substituents in the benzene ring enhances the rate of oxidation while that of opposite one retards it. The small ρ value suggests a mechanism with little charge separation. The rate of oxidation depends on the nature of alkyl group and conformational effects.

Kinetics of aromatic acetals by various oxidants have been reported¹. With a view to testing the applicability of linear free energy relationship and thereby gaining for the insight into the mechanism, we have studied the kinetics of several aromatic acetals with different substituents in the benzene ring and alcohol moieties. The results are analysed using Hammett equation and conformational effects.

Results and Discussion

The salient features of this investigation are given below. The plots of log absorbance vs time are linear showing that the reaction is first order rate in oxidant. The near constancy in pseudo-first order constants (k_{obs}) at different concentrations of oxidant confirms the first order dependence of oxidant. Moreover, the plot of log k_{obs} vs log [acetal] is also linear ($r = 0.99$) with a unit slope. The second order rate constants (k_2) are found to be constant. Hence, the reaction between acetals and PFC is governed by the simple rate expression,

$$\frac{-d[\text{PFC}]}{dt} = k [\text{Acetal}] [\text{PFC}]$$

The rate of oxidation is decreased with increase in the polarity of the medium. This shows that oxidation is facilitated by the decrease in water content of the solvent mixture. A good correlation exist between log k_{obs} and the inverse of dielectric constant ($r = 0.99$) with a positive slope. This may be due to the presence of interaction between a positive ion and a dipole². The acid-catalysed nature of this oxidation is confirmed by the increase in the rate of oxidation by the addition of *p*-toluene sulphonic acid (PTSA). This shows that the protonated PFC may function as the effective oxidant³ similar to that of chromium trioxide oxidation⁴,

A perusal of the rate data (Table 1) shows that electron-withdrawing substituents increase the rate while those of opposite ones retard it⁵. The order of reactivities in respect of substituents in the benzene ring is $p\text{-NO}_2 > m\text{-NO}_2 > m\text{-Cl} > p\text{-Cl} > \text{H} > p\text{-Me} > p\text{-OMe}$.

The rate of oxidation is much more influenced by the alcohol moieties present in the acetals. The order of reactivities with respect to alcohol moiety in acetal is benzyl > isoamyl > *n*-butyl > isobutyl > *n*-propyl. The plot of log k_2 (333 K) vs log k_2 (313 K) is linear for all the acetals showing that they undergo oxidation with similar mechanism⁶.

Table 1. Rate constant and activation parameters for PFC oxidation of aromatic acetals

Solvent : AcOH-H₂O (4 : 1), [PFC] = 1.00 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, [Acetal] = 1.00 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³

	$k_{\text{obs}} \times 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1}$			ΔH^\ddagger	ΔS^\ddagger	ΔG^\ddagger
	313 K	323 K	333 K	kJ mol ⁻¹	J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	kJ mol ⁻¹
	R = <i>n</i> -Butyl,					
	X =					
<i>p</i> -NO ₂	3.5	5.4	7.1	27.6	-121.9	65.7
<i>m</i> -NO ₂	3.2	4.9	6.4	27.0	-121.6	65.3
<i>m</i> -Cl	2.6	3.4	4.8	20.9	-140.7	64.9
<i>p</i> -Cl	2.2	3.0	4.2	23.8	-130.5	64.6
<i>p</i> -Me	1.4	2.5	3.8	39.2	-77.0	63.3
<i>p</i> -OMe	0.42	0.69	0.99	34.5	-81.7	66.1
	X = H, R =					
<i>n</i> -Propyl	0.24	0.45	0.70	50.2	-26.9	58.6
iso-Butyl	1.5	2.4	3.3	33.7	-94.7	63.4
<i>n</i> -Butyl	1.8	2.7	3.9	29.9	-108.8	64.0
iso-Amyl	2.3	4.0	5.5	35.2	-93.8	64.5
Benzyl	8.5	11.7	16.4	28.4	-136.4	68.1

The plot of $\log K_{\text{obs}/kH}$ vs σ does not give a satisfactory correlation ($r = 0.878$), whereas the plot of $\log k_{\text{obs}/kH}$ vs σ^+ is linear ($r = 0.95$) with a low positive ρ value (0.53). A small ρ often means that the mechanism of this reaction involves radical intermediate or some other mechanism with little charge separation. The absence of induced polymerization by the addition of methyl methacrylate under nitrogen atmosphere rules out free radical mechanism. The negative salt-effect indicates that the reaction may proceed through transition state⁷ which may be less polar than the reactant (Scheme 1). The effect of al-

Scheme 1

cohol moiety is more pronounced than the substituents in the benzene ring. The Taft⁸ polar plot of $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ vs σ^+ for alkyl group is linear ($r = 0.98$) with a negative slope, which indicates that electron-donating nature of alkyl group accelerates the rate of oxidation. This oxidation may be viewed as oxidative dealkylation reaction. During oxidation, the cleavage of oxygen-alkyl (O-R) bond and the formation of C=O double bond may be simultaneous. The order of reactivity may be explained if the stability of carbocation and conformational effects are taken into account.

Only primary carbocation may be formed by the cleavage O-R bond. The stability of carbocation depends on resonance stabilization and length of carbocation. Benzyl carbocation is stabilized to a greater extent by resonance, which reflects in greater reactivity. Similarly, the low reactivity of *n*-propylacetal may be due to the least stability of *n*-propyl cation. The cleavage of O-R bond

may also depend on conformational effect. Three conformations are possible (C_1 , C_2 and C_3) (Fig. 1). During oxidation it is found that rate is accelerated by the increase in the length of alkyl chain and branching on β -carbon except benzylacetal. The favourable conformations C_1 or C_2 may

Fig. 1. Conformations

be involved during oxidation. These conformers may have less torsional energy than C_3 conformer. The cleavage O-R bond depends on the interaction between the developing vacant orbital on benzal carbon produced by the removal of hydride ion and filled *p*-orbital on oxygen. The formation of C=O may be accelerated by the electron-withdrawing group and retarded by the opposite one. On the other hand, cleavage of O-R bond may be made easier by the electron-donating capacity of the R group and the stability of carbocation. Contrary to acetal hydrolysis⁹, during oxidation of acetal O-R cleavage may be preferred even when R is chosen deliberately so as to make R^+ a poor cation. In order to assume the required conformation during oxidation the molecules have to surrender the freedom of taking other possible arrangements. This may lead to considerable reduction in entropy as found experimentally.

Experimental

All the chemicals were of A.R. grade. Acetals were prepared by the reported procedure and characterised by IR and NMR spectral data. PFC was prepared by the reported method¹⁰. Acetic acid was purified and distilled.

For the kinetic measurement, the reactions were studied under pseudo-first order condition by maintaining a large excess of acetal over PFC. The required percentage of acetic acid was prepared using conductivity water. Kinetics runs were followed colorimetrically (Erma AE 11 S). The rate constants calculated by the least-square method were reproducible with in $\pm 3\%$. The oxidation products of the corresponding esters were separated and characterised by IR and NMR spectral data.

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